

ATTENTION TO WOMEN IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This article is aimed at ensuring gender equality in the protection of women's rights in Uzbekistan, increasing their social participation in society, attaching importance to vocational education, the implementation of their wishes and aspirations. plans and proposals for sensible policies to support and the achievements of our women today, their place in society and the resulting changes, as well as the implementation of new political and social reforms, drawing conclusions from these methods.

Keywords: women, law, interest, reform, profession, education, International Labor Organization, decision, state program, national mechanism, entrepreneurship

Introduction. Soon it will be 30 years of independence of our country. The results of large-scale reforms carried out in our country during this period are reflected, first of all, in the fact that our life becomes more prosperous, and our achievements receive due recognition of the world community. We should be glad to see our compatriots, regardless of gender, age and nationality, who contribute to the development of our country. Anyone who performs such an honorable duty to the Motherland deserves pride. They deserve respect, especially if they are women who are weak by nature and doomed only to obedience. Unfortunately, thousands of our women are still victims of deprivation. This is a betrayal not only for the unborn child, but also for the future of the whole country, forcing parents to marry their daughters, ignoring the talents and interests of their daughters. If such cases were not allowed and special attention was paid to the profession and education of women, then the number of helpless women who unfortunately divorced and did not know where to turn their heads would not be the same as now ... To prevent such disappointments, our people and our country. It would be a great light if we set before our society the goal of making everyone accountable to contribute to their

interests, as well as paying particular attention to the role and status of women in society.

It is interesting to note that the political activity of women, who make up more than half of the world's population, has not been fully reflected in society, not only in the East, where family values are preserved more than careers, but also in the West, where equality is at its peak. If women ruled the world, that is, if their positions in economics and politics were increased, they would pay more attention to problems that are neglected in society, put an end to the wars that are shaking the world and strive for social justice, questions are asked. Research shows that women's leadership styles differ from men's: they try to be more cooperative and rely on public opinion. Recent observations show that women leaders are paying more attention to improving education and health, providing the population with clean drinking water and taking their actions seriously. health. Women starting businesses start hiring other women. This leads to the employment of women and their participation in public life, freedom of thought. It is known from history that famous rulers such as Tomaris, Nefertiti, Elizabeth I, who, thanks to their originality in women's politics and acceptable methods of government, could rule the entire state, were Nobel laureates. awards such as Marie Curie, Rosalyn Franklin. and Maria Goeppert Mayer, we all know that women's discoveries have brought about significant changes in modern scientific life. Seeing that women who are considered vulnerable and who do not have the same rights as men have been able to seize power around the world, we can confidently say that women of our time can do such great things, and we will try to create the necessary conditions for them. helping them do such great things.

Well-known politicians also speak positively about the role of women in society. "When a woman is in power, she thinks about the fate of her children and grandchildren in every decision she makes," said former Irish President Mary Robinson. Former US Secretary of State Condoleezza Rice also commented on women's activism: "There is a great need for the development of society. The role of women in peace processes is invaluable because they strive to protect their families. Women suffer the most in conflicts. "

As a result of the priority of protecting human rights and freedoms, our legitimate interests, our attitude towards family and women has changed, and respect for them has become the meaning and purpose of our life. As the head of our state acknowledged in his congratulatory message to the women of Uzbekistan in March this year, it was during the period of independence that we

seem to have rediscovered a lot. We understand that the idea that if a woman is beautiful - the world is beautiful, if a woman is happy - family, the whole society will be happy, is deeply rooted in our consciousness and becomes our philosophy of life. The measures formed on the basis of this vision are based on the proposals and principles of full support for women and their contribution not only to their prosperous future, but also to the development of society as a whole.

Among the topical issues raised in the book of the first President Islam Karimov "Uzbekistan on the threshold of independence" is the creation of favorable conditions for the participation of women in public production and management in order to properly guarantee the protection of the socio-political rights of women and their prestige. It is noted that the protection of maternal and child health, education and culture of the population should be ensured in all socio-economic and ideological aspects. This shows that from the first years of independence, taking care of women, increasing their political activity, raising their professional, physical, spiritual and intellectual potential, guiding girls to modern professions, attracting them to sports, protecting motherhood and childhood, the formation of a healthy family has risen to the level of public policy.

In recent years, thirteen women who selflessly worked in the fields of production, education, health care and agriculture were awarded the title "Hero of Uzbekistan", and many of our women were awarded state awards. Establishment of the State Prize. Zulfiya for girls and the fact that hundreds of talented people have been awarded this award so far, in fact, testifies to the attention paid to them. Every woman living in Uzbekistan today is truly happy. In the end, his rights and freedoms are enshrined in law, and his goals are raised to the level of the goals of society. The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dozens of laws, about eighty decrees and resolutions, state programs serve as the legal basis for increasing the social and political activity of women, strengthening their status in the family and society, protecting the family, motherhood and motherhood, and childhood.

At the same time, although our country has joined various conventions, agreements and treaties, it is important to focus on protecting the rights of women, mothers and children. In particular, the UN Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (SYeDAW), Political Rights of Women, International Labor Organization for the Protection of Maternity and Discrimination in Labor and Employment. The conventions

and a number of other international instruments are reflected in our national legislation and their implementation is ensured.

The decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to enhance the role of women in the state and social construction of the Republic of Uzbekistan" marked a new stage in the consistent continuation of reforms in this area. Consequently, the document adopted twenty years ago laid the foundations for a national mechanism for the advancement of women at the executive level, paving the way for the implementation of state programs for the socio-economic and political development of women. Accordingly, a new post of Deputy Prime Minister of the Republic of Uzbekistan has been introduced, who will be responsible for resolving issues related to further increasing the role of women in public life.

In 1996, the Cabinet of Ministers adopted the Concept for the Improvement of the Status of Women in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The submission of the National Report on the Implementation of the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Girls serves to realize the constitutional rights of women.

The wise policy pursued in the country today makes the dreams of our sisters come true. In the stories of our mothers and grandmothers, we often hear that in the former Soviet Union, women lived within four walls, and that mothers did not spare themselves for the "plan", kissing their children in the poisonous cotton fields. No matter how hard it was, no matter how much oppression our women were subjected to, endurance, perseverance, self-sacrifice, hard work, in short, tolerance made them heroes of today's healing days, a symbol of loyalty and tenderness. Fortunately, the current era is truly becoming a symbol of a truly free life for women. Their rights are protected, the most necessary and necessary conditions are created for their peaceful life.

Achieving social equality is a complex and lengthy process that depends on the level of social development, economic opportunities, ideological programs, cultural and spiritual potential of the country. Creating opportunities for involving women in various spheres of life and work, developing and implementing long-term state policy in this area, aimed at improving the social status of women in accordance with the current economic conditions, will strengthen their place in the world. society. Our country pays great attention to this. And this is not accidental, because in Uzbekistan women make up a large number of strata of society, have their own mental and demographic characteristics, different functions and a certain social status. Harnessing the

enormous potential of women and empowering women to achieve their goals will contribute to the rapid economic, social and political growth and development of the country. Discussion of the preparation of active women with the appropriate skills and abilities for leadership positions, the full support of women entrepreneurs, especially the development of family businesses, will be a leading help in this direction. Focusing on measures to reduce crime against women will also help them escape crime scenes and regain their place in society.

Women who took to the streets of crime did not stand aside. On the occasion of the twenty-fourth anniversary of the adoption of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, at the suggestion of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Act on the Application of Amnesty was adopted in accordance with the principles of humanity. adopted unanimously. According to the law approved by the senators, women who have committed crimes can be pardoned under an amnesty. Last year, President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev pardoned one woman on the occasion of the 28th anniversary of the Constitution. On May 21, 2020, 258 people were returned to their homes from penitentiary institutions. In addition, last year, two Uzbek women serving sentences in correctional institutions of the Republic of Turkmenistan were released under an amnesty and returned to our country. All this is done so that women can learn from their mistakes, properly spend the rest of their lives and have a place in society. We hope women offenders take advantage of this opportunity. There is a saying among the people: it is better to prevent a disease than to cure. " I mean, it's more important to focus on them before they commit the crime, rather than after they commit it. It would be more profitable for society to focus on the problem of concern to them before they are forced to commit a crime, to the extent that this can replace amnesty.

In Uzbekistan, too, special attention is paid to women who have fallen into the trap of religious fanaticism and have joined extremist groups abroad. This is evidenced by the return of 156 Uzbeks (48 women and 106 children) from Syria on a special flight on May 30, 2019 as part of the humanitarian operation "Mercy" ("Mehr"). President Shavkat Mirziyoyev said the government should provide medical, psychological, material and spiritual assistance to people who "left for another country as a result of deception and went through a difficult period of life" so that they could return to a peaceful life and adapt to society. It was noted that it is necessary to create the necessary conditions for participation in educational and social programs, take measures to provide housing and employment and provide them with assistance. Three women who joined the

Islamic State (IS) extremist group were pardoned in August and four in December.

Unfortunately, it was not possible to return all the women and children detained in the camp. Tanzila Norbaeva, chair of the Women's Committee of Uzbekistan, said that the operation to remove women and children from the conflict zones in the Middle East will not end there and the practice of their return will continue. The saddest thing is that among them there are women who call Uzbekistan a "state of unbelief" and prefer to stay in these conflict zones. It is heartbreaking to see how these women, who have become real mangroves, destroy the future of themselves and their children with their own hands. It is not hard to see why such blind women are mistakenly in such a predicament. The reason for all this is the neglect of women. If attention was paid to the timely spirituality, education and advancement of women in the country who preferred this bloody land to their peaceful homeland, they would not be so devoted to fanaticism, and their children would become fathers. are they forced to pay for their future because of the mistake of their mother? ... If we begin to see women not as ordinary weak ones, but as educators of young people who are the future of our country, we will contribute to the bright future of our country. country. Let us not be indifferent to the pain, conditions and life of women around us. Let's not just wait for the government to help them, but just pay attention to them as ordinary people. All the mistakes they make are due to our negligence. We must not forget that in a country where a woman is considered sacred, special attention should be paid to her rights, desires and desires.

When it comes to increasing the social activity of women with disabilities, it is important to provide psychological support and support when working with this category of women. At the same time, attention should be paid to improving the social conditions for them and providing them with employment opportunities.

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